

A STUDY ON IDOL WORSHIP

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ABSTRACT

Idol worship is one of the religious phenomena that has existed from ancient times to the present. In Islam in particular, it is strongly condemned as a grave act of shirk (polytheism) against Allah. In this paper, based on the work "Iman" by Sheikh Muhammad Sadiq Muhammad Yusuf (an Islamic scholar from Uzbekistan), a partial translation is provided along with an analysis of the reality of idol worship.

One form of committing shirk against Allah is the worship of idols and images. In the belief of idol worshippers, idols are considered to possess special powers and to be entities that transcend nature. Various myths and legends have been created about idols. Some idols are called "gods of war," others "gods of fertility." In addition, people have believed in many "gods," such as "gods of good and evil," "goddesses of love," "gods of rain," and "spirits of the mountains."

It is narrated that even a wise and intelligent person like Hazrat Umar, during the period of polytheism, engaged in actions that are difficult to accept rationally. During a journey, he wished to perform prayer but realized that he had left his "god" at home. After some thought, he took dates from his bag, shaped them into an idol, and prayed to it.

Later, continuing his journey, he became tired and hungry. He then took out that "god" from his bag and ate it. After satisfying his hunger, he came to his senses, realized the absurdity of worshipping something he could eat, and, recognizing his foolishness, reportedly laughed and collapsed.

Why did the Arabs worship stones and metals that could neither benefit nor harm them? The answer is given by the idol worshippers themselves. In the Qur'an, their words are mentioned as follows:

"We worship them only so that they may bring us nearer to Allah."

(They knew that these entities neither created nor provided sustenance. They only hoped that they would intercede for them before Him.) (Surah Az-Zumar, 39:3)

A similar idea is expressed by modern idol worshippers. According to them, having an idol or image in front of the worshipper helps concentrate the mind, brings them closer to Allah, and aids deeper contemplation.

However, worshipping idols, prostrating before them, believing them to be symbols of Allah, and assuming that only through them one can approach Allah is not logically sound. This is because the idol placed before the worshipper diverts attention away from direct

connection with Allah and from reflecting upon His true power. Approaching Allah is achieved not through any image or object, but through direct worship of Allah Himself.

Conclusion

From the above discussion based on the Sheikh's statements, it can be concluded that idol worship only distances humans from Allah, the One truly worthy of worship. While idol worship influences human thought and belief, it can lead people away from true faith. To draw closer to Allah, it is essential to worship Him directly, without any intermediaries such as images or objects. Logically speaking, how can a human worship something made by their own hands? An idol that can be shattered with a single blow cannot even protect itself—how, then, can it protect humans? Why do people of reason not reflect on this?

References:

1. Sheikh Muhammad Sadiq Muhammad Yusuf, "Iman"

